

PROSODY AS THE GRAMMATICAL COMPLEXITY OF THE SPOKEN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article is devoted to some challenges that can occur in a variety languages when pronouncing the linguistic utterances, their formation and their usage in communication.

Keywords: The descriptive approach to the Language, The Theory of Constituency and Recursion, The theory of Modularity, The descriptive approach to the Language

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена проблемам, которые могут возникнуть в разных языках при произношении лингвистических слов и при их употреблении и образовании в общении

Ключевой слова: Описательный подход к языку, Теория конституции и рекурсии, Теория модульности, Описательный подход к языку

Annotasiya: Ушбу мақолада лингвистик сўзларни талаффуз қилишда ва уларни мулоқотда қўллашда ва шакллантиришда турли тилларда юзага келиши мумкин бўлган муоммаларга тўхталиб ўтилган

Kalit so'zlar: Тилга тафсифий ёндашув, Конституция ва рекурсия назарияси, Модуллиқ назарияси,

A precise definition of language is not easy to provide, because the language phenomenon is complex. Slightly modifying a definition provided by Finegan and Besnier (1989), we might define language as a finite system of elements and principles that make it possible for speakers to construct sentences to do particular communicative

jobs. The part of the system that allows speakers to produce and interpret grammatical sentences is called grammatical competence. It includes the knowledge of what speech sounds are part of a given language and how they may and may not be strung together. Grammatical competence also includes knowing the meanings signified by different sound sequences in a language and how to combine those units of meaning into words, phrases and sentences. Grammatical competence is what allows a speaker of English to string together 21 sounds that sound something like “The dog chased the cat up the tree” and allows another speaker of English to understand what dogs, cats, and trees are, what chasing is, and which way is up. Further, grammatical competence is what allows these speakers of English to share the understanding that it was the dog doing the chasing and that it was the cat that went up the tree. Of course this does not apply only to English. Grammatical competence contributes similarly to comprehension in all human languages. But people use language to do far more than just communicate the literal meanings of grammatical sentences. The sentence “The dog chased the cat up the tree” might be used to accomplish a wide variety of jobs: to narrate part of a story, to complain to the dog’s owner, to help the cat’s owner find his pet. The second part of the definition, “to do particular communicative jobs,” refers to the notion communicative competence. The most frequent “job” that people do with language is communicating with other people. Grammatical competence is almost useless for human interaction without communicative competence. In fact, a lot of the actual use of language is not in sentences at all, but in discourse units larger and smaller than sentences, some grammatical (in the technical sense used in formal linguistics), some not. To be effective, speakers have to combine grammatical competence with the knowledge of how to use grammatical sentences (and other pieces of linguistic structure) appropriately to the purpose and context at hand. The two taken together comprise communicative competence. Communicative competence – the knowledge included in grammatical Defining language Introduction 9 competence plus the ability

to use that knowledge to accomplish a wide range of communicative jobs – constitutes language.

Speaking involves stringing sounds together into larger units. Aspects of speech that influence stretches of sound larger than a single segment are called suprasegmentals. Suprasegmental aspects of speech include length, tone, intonation, syllable structure, and stress. Because suprasegmental aspects of speech involve the organization of sounds into larger units, the study of suprasegmentals straddles the domains of phonetics (the study of speech sounds as physical objects) and phonology (the study of how languages organize sounds into different patterns).

Tone and intonation The pitch of the voice carries a lot of information. It can tell you whether the speaker is a male or female, a large person or small, old or young. High pitch can tell you that a person is frightened; low pitch that he/she is angry. This sort of information isn't really linguistic, however, but physical or emotional. The terms tone and intonation refer to linguistic uses of pitch. Tone refers to the use of pitch to convey meaning at the word level; intonation refers to the use of pitch to convey meaning at the sentence or discourse level. Intonation distinguishes different kinds of sentences or focuses attention on a particular word. For example, try reading the following sentences out loud (and dramatically): "That's a cat?" "Yup. That's a cat." "A cat? I thought it was a mountain lion!" The pitch of your voice moves in different directions on the word cat. On the first cat, pitch goes up, indicating a question. On the second, pitch falls, indicating a statement or confirmation. On the third cat, a more complicated fall-rise pattern indicates incredulity. (Typographically, we indicate these different "readings" with a question mark, period, and italics, respectively.) In each case, the sequence [khQt] refers to the same object, a feline. The pitch differences indicate only the role that the reference to the feline is playing in the current conversation: asking for information about the cat, providing it, or expressing disbelief regarding the information offered. All languages use intonation to some extent, though the patterns and meanings differ across languages. In addition to intonation, most

languages also use pitch to distinguish different words. In English, whether you say [khQt] with a rising pitch or falling pitch, the word still refers to a feline. In Thai, if you say [kha:] with rising pitch, it means ‘leg’; but if you say it with falling pitch, it means ‘value.’ (There are actually five contrasting pitch patterns in Thai: high, low, mid, falling, and rising.) These words are as different as cat and cut to an English speaker. This use of pitch, to distinguish different words, is known as tone. Although the idea of tones seems very strange to English speakers, the majority of the world’s languages are tonal. The major European languages and their relatives are exceptional in not having tone.

Syllable structure How many syllables are in the word *Appalachicola*? *Massachusetts*? *Antidisestablishmentarianism*? (6, 4, and 11, respectively.) English speakers have little trouble counting the number of syllables in a word, but linguists have a harder time defining what a syllable is. One preliminary answer might be “a vowel and its surrounding consonants.” Most of the syllables we encounter in English, in words like *pin*, *print*, or even *sprints*, fit this definition. However, it’s perfectly possible to have a syllable without a vowel. We would all agree that *hidden* has two syllables, even if pronounced [hIdn], with no vowel between the two consonants. Also, defining a syllable as “a vowel and the consonants around it” doesn’t explain why some sequences of consonants are allowed and others are not. The sequence [prInt] is acceptable as a syllable in English, but the sequence [rpItn] is not acceptable as a single syllable in any language. Why is [prInt] a good syllable when [rpItn] is not? The best answer (though not perfect) lies in the concept of sonority. Sonority can be defined as relative openness of the vocal tract, which corresponds directly to the relative loudness of a sound. The most sonorous sounds are the low vowels; the mouth is wide open, and the sound flows freely out. The least sonorous sounds are the voiceless stops; the mouth is completely shut, and no sound is made at all. Other sounds range between these two extremes. The speech stream is organized into peaks and valleys of sonority. Languages generally do not choose long strings of consonants nor long strings of vowels. Rather, we alternate sounds that are more

sonorous and less sonorous: each stands out better against the background of the other. A syllable, then, may be defined as a way of organizing sounds around a peak of sonority. Take the simple syllable pin. The vowel [i] is the most sonorous sound in the sequence, flanked by less sonorous consonants. Thus there is a single sonority peak, and a single syllable. The syllable print also follows the principle of sonority. Sonority rises from [p] (voiceless stop) to [r] (rhotic) to [i] (vowel), then falls from vowel to [n] (nasal) to [t] (stop). A single peak, a single syllable. Meanwhile, the sequence [rpiɳt] has three peaks; higher sonority [r], [i], and [ɳ] are interrupted by lowest sonority [p] and [t]. Thus (if it is pronounceable at all) it has three syllables, not one. The most sonorous element of a syllable, the peak itself, is called the nucleus. Lower sonority sounds preceding the nucleus are called the onset; those following the nucleus are called the coda. The nucleus and coda together form the rhyme.

Since vowels are the most sonorous sounds, they usually constitute syllable nuclei, but that's not always the case. Sounds other than vowels may form sonority peaks, so that hidden and prism have one vowel but two syllables. Sonority thus seems to capture most of our intuitions about syllable structure and explains a lot about possible syllables in the languages of the world. But sonority doesn't account for everything. There are some English words that clearly violate the principle of sonority – sprints and sixths, for example. Linguists aren't sure exactly how to deal with words like this. It may be that endings like plural [s] and ordinal [T] are not really part of the syllable at all; rather they're tacked on in an "appendix" to the end of the word. Stress Linguistic stress is a prominence relation between syllables: certain syllables are longer, louder, higher-pitched, or more clearly articulated than those around them. Just as we can generally count the syllables in a word, we can generally pick out the syllable that's most prominent: phoNOlogy, phoNEtics, SYNtax. There are at least three different levels of stress in English. Consider the word Alabama. The third syllable [bQ] is the most prominent, and bears the main or primary stress of the word, but the other three syllables do not receive equal stress. The first syllable has a full vowel

quality [Q], though it is not quite as long or loud as the third, but the second and fourth syllables are short and weak, with the tongue not moving far from its central position. We say that the first syllable has secondary stress, while the second and fourth are completely unstressed. Some languages do not use stress at all. In Japanese, for example, all the syllables in a word are sometimes pronounced with equal prominence. This gives quite a bit of trouble to English speakers. In 1996, for example, when the Winter Olympics were held in Japan, English commentators had a great deal of trouble deciding how to say the name of the host city: NAgano? NaGAno? NagaNO? In fact, the word is pronounced with all syllables equally stressed (or equally unstressed), a difficult task for an English speaker. Conversely, Japanese speakers often have a great deal of trouble with reducing the unstressed vowels of English, sounding overly careful to English ears. Because stress is a prominence relation, stressed and unstressed syllables tend to alternate across the word: ApalachiCOla, for instance. In order for a syllable to be heard as prominent, it helps if it's surrounded by nonprominent syllables. In English, stress sometimes even moves around in order to accommodate an alternating pattern. In a word like sixteen, stress usually falls on the second syllable (How old are you? SixTEEN.). But put the word next to one that begins with a strongly stressed syllable, and stress may shift back in order to maintain an alternating pattern (How long have you worked here? "SIXteen YEARS.) Linguists refer to a grouping of a stressed syllable and adjacent unstressed syllables as a foot. Choosing different kinds of feet (da-DUM vs. DA-dum) is important not only in poetry, but as part of defining a language's unfolding rhythm of speech.

Languages in which stress is completely predictable are called fixed stress systems. Fixed stress may be alternating, as in Pintupi, an Australian language where stress always falls on the first syllable and then on every other syllable after that: [KUr^uraululimpatjura] 'the first one (who is) our relation.' Other fixed stress systems may pick out just one syllable in the word as especially prominent. In Farsi, stress is always on the initial syllable, in Turkish always on the last syllable, in Polish always

on the second-to-last syllable. In other languages, stress is unpredictable: you just have to memorize which syllable gets stressed when you learn the word, in the same way you have to memorize whether it begins with [b] or [p]. This is called lexical stress. For example, Russian has a lexical stress system: if stress is placed on the first syllable, [dʊxi] means ‘spirits’; stressed on the second syllable, it means ‘perfume.’ The third type of system is paradigmatic stress, in which the stress patterns depend on what part of speech a word is – for example, a noun or a verb. The English system is mostly paradigmatic, with some unpredictable aspects. Generally, English verbs and adjectives follow one set of rules, nouns another. Thus English has pairs of words that differ only in stress, where one word is a noun and the other a verb: we reJECT the REject, reCORD the REcord, conVERT the CONvert, inSULT with an INsult, etc

The term intonation refers to the variations in speech melody that speakers/listeners code/ decode in order to interpret the syntactic structure of a sentence and its grammatical and pragmatic meanings. The interpretation is bound to the prosodic structure. The intonation contours depend on two aspects of the prosodic structure the metrical positions of prominence and the edges of prosodic categories (Pierrehumbert 1999). We looked at the prosodic categories in the past three modules. Intonation is a unique phonological phenomenon, essentially because it is meaningful in itself, such as the Falling tone standing for ‘declarative’ and a rising tone for an ‘interrogative’ statement, and it alone has pragmatic functions such as ‘attitude’ and ‘emotions’¹

Various ways of carrying out intonational analysis have been proposed since the time of Palmer (1922). (We should note that a good deal of the discussion in this section is based on Ladd (2008[1996].) Some of the prominent ones are the following approaches:

a) The British School approach b) American Structuralist approach c) Pierre Humbert’s model a. Tone and Break Indices (ToBI) b. The Autosegmental-Metrical

¹ Fox, Anthony. (2000). Prosodic features and prosodic structure: The phonology of suprasegmentals. New York: Oxford University Press.

(A-M) model ²(Ladd 1996, Gussenhoven 2004) d) The OT model (Gussenhoven 2004) The British school laid emphasis on the tonal structure of a tone unit as consisting of the parts- (Pre-Head) (Head) Nucleus (Tail). We discussed this approach in Module 29 of Course 2. It employed mainly the impressionistic method. It is, however, eminently usable with experimental validation. British phoneticians (e.g. Kingdom 1958, O'Connor & Arnold 1961) continued to pursue this approach, widely used language teaching. The American Structuralist model was followed in the period before the coming of Generative Grammar. Pike (1945) presented the four-level model of an intonational unit, resulting in widely used publications on intonation (e.g. Trager & Smith 1957, Gleason 1955 and Hockett 1958). The model consisted in considering the pitch level as the basic unit of intonation. The pitch levels for speakers with different ranges of F0 were normalized in terms of four levels- 1 (extra-high), 2 (high), mid (3) and 4 (low).

(1) The allowance of a combination of the two levels gives the following contours- Fall (HL), Rise (LH), Fall-Rise (HLH) and Rise –Fall (LHL). This idea was directly drawn from Auto segmental Phonology. The reduction of pitch levels to two gave a constrained theory of levels and allowed for a limited set of contrasts in phonological tone.³

(2) Intonation patterns for different types of sentences. Languages distinguish between different sentence types with differences in the intonational contours. Most typically, IPs of declaratives end in an L tone, while IPs of interrogatives end in a H tone. However, in many languages, interrogatives don't always end in H tone. There are however, different types of interrogatives, such as Wh-questions, Yes/No questions, Tag questions. Language use different intonational features to distinguish them. For lack of space, we are not able to go into the details of the topic. But the literature is full of the intonation patterns of different types of sentences in different

² Ladd, D. R. (1996/2008). *Intonational Phonology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

³ The same source

languages. Jun (2005, 2014) are useful references for a discussion of a wide ranging variety of intonational phenomena in different languages. 6. Tones and Break Indices (ToBI)

The A-M model of intonation has been used to propose a system for prosodic transcription, known as Tones and Break Indices (ToBI). The ToBI system has been in use for many languages with minor differences, such as MAE_ToBI for Mainstream American English (Beckman & Ayers Elam 1997), D-ToBI for Dutch (Gussenhoven 2007) G-ToBI for German (Baumann, Grice, and Benzmueller 1995), JToBI for Japanese (Jun 2000) and B-ToBI for Bengali (Khan 2008). Gussenhoven (2000:11), for example, proposes the following pitch accents and boundary tones for D-ToBI: (9) The ToBI systems include an inventory of pitch accents and boundary tones. They also contain the descriptions of their phonetic realization and the nature of phonological interaction between them. A feature common to the phonetic implementation of the example of pitch accents 15 and boundary tones is the phenomenon of declination found in most languages, which involves a gradual fall of pitch from the beginning to the end of an utterance. In tonal languages, it is termed downdrift. For example, look at the alignment of pitch track and prominence in an utterance in Assamese⁴ (Twaha 2017):

Figure 13: the alignment of pitch track and prominence in an utterance in Assamese/indo
(Twaha 2017)

⁴ Twaha, A. I. (2017). Intonational Phonology and Focus in Two Varieties of Assamese. Ph. D. thesis. IIT Guwahati. Guwahati.

Note the gradual fall in pitch from the first Hp (the boundary tone at the PP level). As an attempt at bringing the tonal contours close to phonetic realization, it is common practice to propose modified contours, including differences in duration and pitch levels. Thus, for the tonal contours of Dutch in the D-ToBI, Gussenhoven also proposes the following modified tones: (10) Modified pitch accents in D-ToBI !H* !H*L L*HL L*!HL H*+L 16 Gussenhoven explains them thus: “First, H* and H*L may be downstepped, notated !H* and !H*L. Second, (!)H*L may be prefixed with L*, leading to the tritonal pitch accents L*HL and L*!HL, to be used for (downstepped or non-downstepped) delayed falls and fall-rises (cf. Ladd 1983, Gussenhoven 1983). Lastly, a prefinal steep fall is transcribed H*+L to distinguish it from the gradual prefinal fall.” (p.12) There are some topics that could not be taken up for discussion here, but that are of critical significance in the study of intonation. Two of the prominent ones are: (a) the features of the effect of Focus, in particular, and information structure, in general, on intonational contours, and (b) prosodic processing. In addition, (c) the issue of typology of intonation types in world languages is of much interest in the study of intonational phonology. Readers are advised to look up some of the following references on the topics: (a) Féry et al. (2007), (b) Féry (Chapter 2016), (c) Gussenhoven (2004) and Féry (2016). These contain insightful overviews of the literature on the topics.

7. Summary

In the present module, we looked at some of the fundamental aspects of intonational phonology. We began with a brief review of theoretical models for the study of intonation and focused on the A-M model that is in current use. We also discussed some of the prominent aspects of the intonation of Accentual Phrase and Intonational Phase before moving on to discuss the influence of the A-M model in the emergence of ToBI, a widely used transcription system for the study of the intonation of world languages, with many variations.

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